

LINGUISTICS AND ITS CONNECTION BETWEEN OTHER DISCIPLINES. PECULIARITIES OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LINGUISTICS AND LITERARY STUDIES

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Abstract: This article informs readers about linguistics and its correlation with other scientific subjects. It delves into the intricate interplay between linguistics and literary studies, unravelling the multifaceted connections that exist between these two disciplines. Linguistics, as the scientific study of language, serves as a foundational framework for understanding the structure, evolution, and cultural nuances inherent in human communication. This paper explores the symbiotic relationship between linguistics and literary studies, shedding light on the unique dynamics that emerge when these fields intersect.

Key words: Sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, literary studies.

Linguistics is the scientific study of language and its structure. It encompasses the analysis of the many aspects of human language, including its sounds (phonetics and phonology), structure (syntax and morphology), meaning (semantics), and use in context (pragmatics). Linguistics also explores the historical development of languages (diachronic linguistics) and the variation of language in different social and regional contexts (sociolinguistics and dialectology). Linguistics intersects with various other disciplines, and its principles are applied across a wide range of fields due to the central role language plays in human communication and cognition.

Correlation between linguistics and other disciplines

A number of linguistics disciplines study language usage and evolution. For instance, linguists study how languages are learned, developed, and used in diverse socio-economic and ethnic contexts as well as in real-time comprehension and production. These problems are addressed by the following linguistics branches: Historical linguistics studies the evolution and past of language. "Linguistic history is basically the darkest of the dark arts, the only means to conjure up the ghosts of vanished centuries. With linguistic history, we reach farthest back into the mystery: humankind" (Campbell 2013).

Sociolinguistics - the use of language in social circumstances. It is concerned with investigating the relationships between language and society with the goal being a better understanding of the structure of language and of how languages function in communication; the equivalent goal in the sociology of language is trying to discover how social structure can be better understood through the study of language (Ronald Wardhaugh).

Psycholinguistics is the study of how language is produced and understood in real time. Aitchison (1990) defines psycholinguistics as the study of language and mind, which "aims to model the way the mind" works in "relation to language". This description makes it clear that,

in her opinion, psycholinguistics maps out both language comprehension and language usage strategy.

Neurolinguistics: the study of language's neural representation. Neurolinguistics is the study of language-brain relations. Its final goal is the comprehension and explanation of the neural bases for language knowledge and use. Neurolinguistics is by its nature an interdisciplinary enterprise, and straddles the borders between linguistics and other disciplines that are connected to the study of the mind/brain (mainly cognitive psychology, neuropsychology and cognitive neuroscience) (Valentina Bambini).

Many other humanities, social, and natural scientific fields that focus on specific facets of language, such as philosophy, psychology, literature, language teaching and pedagogy, sociology, biology, computer science, and the health sciences, interact with linguistics.

Peculiarities of the connection between linguistics and literary studies

Linguistics and literary studies, both falling under the vast umbrella of philology, explore the intricacies of language but approach this exploration from different angles. While linguistics delves into the scientific study of language, literary studies, or literary criticism, focuses on the analysis and interpretation of literary works. Despite their distinct focuses, these disciplines share common ground, and their symbiotic relationship has been crucial in shaping our understanding of language and literature.

The science of literature is called literary studies, one of the two philological disciplines. Linguistics, from the Latin *lingua*, meaning language, is the other branch of philology. Since each of these fields investigate language-related phenomena in different ways, they have a lot in common. As a result, they have evolved closely together over the ages under the umbrella term "philology" (derived from the Greek words "logos," which means "word," and "phileo," which means "I love"). Despite their shared interests, linguistics and literary studies are separate sciences since they need different kinds of cognitive processes. In order to determine the distinctive features of the legitimate evolution of the languages spoken and written by diverse countries around the world, linguistics investigates a variety of language phenomena, or more specifically, the phenomena of human verbal activity. On the other hand, literary studies look at the creative literature of other countries to identify the unique characteristics and patterns of its content, expressing them in different ways.

However, linguistics and literary studies are always interacting and supporting one another. The fundamental information needed to make linguistic observations and draw conclusions about the overall traits of the languages spoken by various countries comes from literary studies. However, literary works' linguistic quirks are related to the details of their substance just like any other quirk. Linguistics may get important insights into these content-specific features of literary language from literary studies.

In summary, the interdisciplinary field of linguistics and literary studies offers an enthralling domain where language structures meet literary talent. This dynamic relationship develops through a multitude of aspects that deepen our understanding of the subtleties of narrative and textual expression. We investigate the unique characteristics that define the connection between literary studies and linguistics in this investigation.

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